

Studies in the Formation and Properties of Carbon-oxygen Surface Complexes. Part I. Formation of the Complexes on Treatment of Charcoal with Different Oxidising Agents.

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Treatment of charcoal with different oxidising agents results, in some cases, in the fixation of oxygen giving rise to surface oxygen complexes, and, in some other cases, in the elimination of oxygen if already present, the effect varying not only with the nature of the treatment but also with the initial oxygen status of the charcoal. The results indicate that formation of oxygen complexes is a step preceding combustion. The complex capable of evolving carbon dioxide appears to exist in two forms, one of which is acidic and titratable against alkalis, the other is not.

The formation of carbon-oxygen surface compounds due to the union of oxygen atoms with surface carbon atoms of charcoal¹⁻⁴, carbon black⁵⁻⁶, graphite⁷ or diamond^{8,9} has been reported by a number of investigators in recent years and the subject nicely reviewed^{9,10}. These compounds are known to influence several properties of carbon such as acidity^{3,4,11-13}, polarity¹⁴, cation exchange capacity¹⁵, wettability^{16,17}, resistivity¹⁸, selective adsorption^{19,20}, etc. of the carbon. Several hypothetical structures²¹ and formulae have been assigned to these surface oxides and, in recent years, the existence of such functional groups as carboxyls^{4,5,12}, phenols^{4,13}, carbonyls^{4,22}, lactones⁹, quinones^{9,23},

1. Anderson, R. B. and Emmett, P. H., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1947, 51, 1308.
2. Puri B. R., Singh, D. D., Nath, J. and Sharma, L. R., *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1958, 50, 1071.
3. Puri, B. R., *Proc. Fifth Carbon Conf.*, Pergamon Press, p. 165, 1962.
4. Boehm, H. P., Diehl, E., Heck, W. and Sappok, R., *Angew. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 669.
5. Donnet et al., *Compt. rend.*, 1959, 248; 3702, *Bull. Soc. Chim., France*, 1960, 1609; 1962, 1725; *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1963, 60, 426.
6. Anderson, R. B. and Emmett, P. H., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 756.
7. Walker, P. L. Jr., Austin, L. G. and Thijssen, J. J., *Symposium on Carbon*, Tokyo, 1964, VIII-12.
8. Barrer, R. M., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1201.
9. Garten, V. A. and Weiss, D. E., *Rev. Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 1957, 7, 69.
10. Smith, R. N., *Quart. Rev.*, 1956, 13, 287.
11. Weller, S. and Young, T. F., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 4155.
12. Studebaker, M. L., Huffman, E. W. D., Wolfe, A. C. and Nabors, L. G., *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1956, 48, 162.
13. Puri, B. R. and Bansal, R. C., *Carbon*, 1964, 1, 457.
14. Puri, B. R., Murari, K. and Singh, D. D., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 37.
15. Puri, B. R., Singh, G. and Sharma, L. R., *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1958, 17B, 188.
16. Puri, B. R., Singh, D. D. and Sharma, L. R., *J. Phys. Chem.* 1958, 62, 766.
17. Kraus, G., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 343.
18. Studebaker, M. L., *India Rubber World*, 1952, 127, 215, 255.
19. Gasser, C. G. and Kipling, J. J., *Fourth Carbon Conf.*, Pergamon Press, p. 63, 1960.
20. Puri, B. R., Sharma, S. K. and Sandle, N. K., *Ind. J. Chem.* 1963, 1, 418.
21. Schilov, N., Schatunokaja, H. and Tschmutov, K., *Z. Physik. Chim.*, 1930, A 149, 211; 1930, A 150, 31.
22. Smith, W. R. and Schaeffer, W. D., *Rubber Chem. & Tech.*, 1950, 23, 625.
23. Halum, J. V. and Drushel, H. V., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 110.

hydroquinones⁸, chromenes⁹ etc., based on studies of specific chemical reactions or infra-red spectra of the surface oxide layer, has been suggested. However, the various methods of estimation have not yielded comparable results^{4,5} and, what is even more significant, the entire oxygen has not been accounted for¹⁰. The problem of carbon-oxygen surface compounds thus has not been properly elucidated.

In view of the influence of these complexes on surface behaviour of carbons it will be of interest to know more about their formation, nature, structure and properties. The present work was, therefore, undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—Charcoal prepared by the carbonisation of recrystallised cane sugar¹¹ was used as such when it is referred to as 'original' charcoal as well as after outgassing at 400°, 700° and 1000° in the manner described earlier.

Treatments.—The conditions of the various treatments given below were worked out in preliminary experiments for getting maximum fixation of oxygen.

(i) *Treatment with Potassium Persulphate.*—Charcoal (1g.) was mixed with 200 ml. of nearly saturated solution of potassium persulphate in 2*N* sulphuric acid and the suspension shaken for 24 hr.

(ii) *Treatment with Chlorine Water.*—Charcoal (1g.) was mixed with 100 ml. of 0.05*N* chlorine water and the suspension shaken for 24 hr. The clear supernatant liquid was siphoned off, and a fresh lot of 100 ml. of the same chlorine water was added and the suspension shaken again for 24 hr. This was repeated five times.

(iii) *Treatment with Hydrogen Peroxide.*—Charcoal (1g.) was mixed with 100 ml. of 3 *N* H₂O₂ and the suspension shaken for 24 hr.

(iv) *Treatment with Potassium Permanganate.*—Charcoal (1g.) was mixed with 100 ml. of 0.08 *N* KMnO₄ containing excess of sulphuric acid and the suspension shaken for 48 hr.

All the above treatments were done at the room temperature.

(v) *Treatment with Oxygen.*—Pure and dry oxygen was led (@ 2 l./hr.) over 10 g. charcoal placed in a rotating pyrex tube of 3/4" bore heated in a silica tube furnace maintained at 400° for 4 hr. The charcoal was allowed to cool in the atmosphere of oxygen.

(vi) *Treatment with Nitrogen Dioxide.*—Treatment with nitrogen dioxide was given in the same way as with oxygen.

(vii) *Treatment with Superheated Steam.*—Steam prepared in an autoclave was passed through a pre-heater maintained at 1000° and then led over 10g. charcoal placed in a rotating silica tube heated in a furnace maintained at 1000° for 4 hr.

24. deBruin, W. J. and Plasvander, *Physico-chimie du Noir De Carbone*, Mulhouse, France, Sept. 1963, p. 83.

Estimation of Combined Oxygen.—The amount of combined oxygen as well as its disposition as CO_2 , CO & H_2O was obtained in each case on evacuating charcoal (1g.) at 1200° in a resistance tube furnace, raising the temperature of the furnace gradually, and analysing the gases evolved²⁵.

Base-adsorption Capacity.—The base-adsorption capacity was obtained, as before²⁵ by shaking charcoal (1 g.) with 100 ml. of 0.2N barium hydroxide for 48 hr. and titrating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid against a standard acid solution.

Fixation of Bromine.—The amount of bromine fixed was obtained as before²⁵ by shaking charcoal (1 g.) with 200 ml. of bromine water (0.1 N in 0.2 N KBr) in 500 ml. stoppered bottles, wrapped in thick black papers, for 24 hr. and titrating an aliquot for free bromine and hydrobromic acid in the usual way.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Considering the results obtained with the original charcoal (Table I) which contained initially also a large amount of combined oxygen, in the first instance, it is seen that the treatments with potassium persulphate as well as with chlorine and hydrogen peroxide solutions lead to appreciable chemisorption of oxygen, most of which is disposed off as carbon dioxide and practically none as carbon monoxide. The treatment with potassium permanganate solution does not cause any noticeable chemisorption. However, it causes more 'burn off' than the treatment with any other oxidising solution, as indicated by the 'loss in weight'.

The treatments with the oxidising gases (oxygen, nitrogen dioxide and steam) lead to elimination rather than addition of oxygen. The elimination is much more of the oxygen disposed off as carbon dioxide than that of any other form. It appears that the complex capable of evolving carbon dioxide is not only formed but is also eliminated more readily than any other complex. The treatment with steam at such a high temperature as 1000° appears to cause, at first, complete elimination of all the oxygen complexes and then reformation in which the complex capable of evolving carbon dioxide predominates, as expected.

The results of similar experiments with 400° -outgassed charcoal which contained initially a much smaller amount of oxygen than the original charcoal (cf. first lines in Tables I and II) are recorded in Table II. It is seen that the treatments with potassium persulphate solution and chlorine water cause appreciable chemisorption of oxygen, the disposition being again mostly as carbon dioxide. The treatment with hydrogen peroxide and permanganate solutions produce little or no effect while the treatments with oxygen, nitrogen dioxide and steam cause elimination rather than addition of oxygen.

The results with 700° -charcoal which contained initially only a small amount of oxygen disposed off mostly as CO (Table III) and those with 1000° -charcoal which was essentially free of the combined oxygen (Table IV) show that now every treatment leads to chemisorption of oxygen, which is disposed off largely as carbon dioxide. The amount of this oxygen depends upon the nature of the treatment. The complex capable of evolving

carbon monoxide is formed in noticeable amounts only in the case of 1000°-charcoal when treatment is given with potassium permanganate solution, oxygen or nitrogen dioxide. The amount of oxygen chemisorbed is seen to be more in 1000°-than in 700°-charcoal while the amount of combustion is seen to be in the reverse order.

It will be seen on careful examination of the data on 'burn off' of carbon and chemisorption of oxygen in the various samples of charcoal (Tables I to IV) that, generally speaking, the various oxidation treatments cause more combustion and less chemisorption if the initial oxygen content is high, and *vice versa*. This indicates that combustion takes place more readily at the sites occupied by the oxygen complexes while chemisorption takes place more readily at the sites which are free of oxygen. These observations indicate that chemisorption of oxygen is a step preliminary to combustion.

The nature of the CO_n-complex.—The surface acidity (i.e., the base adsorption capacity) of charcoals² as well as carbon blacks²⁶ has been shown to be almost exactly equivalent to the amount of the surface complex capable of evolving carbon dioxide (referred to as CO_n-complex). Since the various oxidation treatments described above cause appreciable formation or elimination of this complex, it was thought of interest to determine the base adsorption capacity (b.a.c.) of each sample before as well as after the treatment. The results are included in Tables I to IV (column 7). The amounts of carbon dioxide evolved, expressed in similar units, are also included in the same column in the parentheses. The difference between the two values, wherever in excess of 2 per cent, is taken as the amount of the non-titratable complex formed during the treatment. These values are given in column 8 of each table.

It is seen that in the original charcoal (Table I) the b.a.c. remains fairly close to the CO_n-complex in all treatments excepting that with steam which will be discussed separately. However, in the 400°-charcoal (Table II) while the treatment with chlorine water produces entirely the titratable complex, the treatments with potassium persulphate, oxygen and nitrogen dioxide give rise partly to the titratable and partly to the non-titratable complex. The treatments with hydrogen peroxide and potassium permanganate solutions do not add up any oxygen while the treatment with steam causes almost complete elimination of the oxygen already present. The results with the 700°- and 1000°-outgassed charcoals (Tables III and IV) show that in the former case all treatments excepting that with chlorine water and in the latter case all treatments without exception give rise to the titratable as well as non-titratable complex and, in many cases, the second complex predominates. The non-titratable complex, observed in the outgassed charcoal only, appears to be formed by the addition of oxygen at the unsaturated sites created by the elimination of gases during the evacuation, the reaction being represented tentatively³ as :

where the circle represents the charcoal surface and -C and -C two surface carbon atoms. Such a complex may evolve carbon dioxide on evacuation but may not react with alkalis. The titratable complex in which two oxygen atoms are assumed to be attached to a single

surface carbon atom²⁷ and which behaves as a layer of 'frozen' carbon dioxide²⁸ probably occupies different sites altogether.

If the oxygen belonging to the non-titratable complex is added up at the unsaturated sites, as suggested above, there should be a corresponding decrease in the amount of surface unsaturation and consequently in the amount of bromine fixed. The results are included in Tables I to IV. It is seen that the amount of bromine fixed by each charcoal decreases in all those cases in which the non-titratable complex is formed and that the decrease is fairly close to the amount of the non-titratable complex formed. This is borne out clearly by the close agreement between the observed and calculated bromine values (given in the parentheses). The calculation of the bromine values in the case of the original charcoal on treatment with steam and in the case of the 400°-outgassed charcoal on treatment with oxygen and nitrogen dioxide needed correction on account of the creation of fresh unsaturated sites as a result of the elimination of chemisorbed oxygen during the treatments. The correction amounts to 1 millieq. of additional bromine for every 2 millieq. of the acidic complex eliminated.²⁵ For example, the 400°-outgassed charcoal on treatment with nitrogen dioxide suffers a loss of 228.168 or 120 millieq. of the acidity. Therefore, the bromine values should rise by 60 millieq. But at the same time 103 millieq. of the non-titratable oxygen is fixed. Therefore, the calculated bromine value is $256 + 60 - 103$ i.e. 213 millieq. which is quite close to the experimental value of 216 millieq. Incidentally, the formation of the non-titratable complex in the case of the original charcoal on treatment with steam is due to elimination of a large amount of the oxygen complexes and therefore creation of unsaturated sites by this drastic treatment.

It is also significant that the formation of the titratable complex does not interfere at all in the bromine value and that in all those cases in which the titratable complex alone is formed (as on treatment of 400°- and 700°- charcoal with chlorine water the bromine values remain practically unchanged).

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